

Prevalence and Associated Factors of Low Birth Weight among Infants in Nepal: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Observational Studies

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Abstract

Low birth weight (LBW) remains a significant public health problem worldwide and is a major contributor to neonatal mortality in developing countries, including Nepal. The Government of Nepal has implemented various programs to improve maternal and neonatal health, including interventions aimed at increasing birth weight. Despite these efforts, LBW continues to pose a substantial maternal and child health challenge. Moreover, maternal and other factors of LBW have been inconsistently assessed in previous studies in Nepal. The primary aim of this systematic review and meta-analysis is to estimate the pooled prevalence of LBW and identify its associated factors in Nepal. The secondary aims are to estimate: the pooled prevalence of more severe forms of LBW, namely, very low birth weight (VLBW) and extremely low birth weight (ELBW), and the pooled mean birth weight in Nepal. Literatures were searched in six electronic databases. Only studies reporting on LBW or VLBW or ELBW infants born in Nepal were included. This research was registered with PROSPERO. Thirty studies with 40,199 subjects were included in this study. The pooled prevalence of LBW was 12% (95% CI: 8%–16%), VLBW was 2% (95% CI: 1%–7%), and ELBW was 1% (95% CI: 0%–3%). The pooled mean birth weight was 2284.74 (95% CI: 1916.18–2653.31) grams. Associated factors of LBW are (preterm birth, gestational age, sex) and maternal factors (age, parity, low weight/BMI, inadequate gestational weight gain, poor nutrition, and insufficient supplementation). One in every eight children in Nepal were born with LBW. The pooled prevalence of VLBW and ELBW was 2% and 1%, respectively. This study provides comprehensive evidence on the prevalence and associated factors of LBW in Nepal, alongside the prevalence of its more severe forms and mean birth weight. Targeted interventions focusing on maternal nutrition, healthcare access, and social inequalities are essential to reduce LBW and improve neonatal outcomes in Nepal.

Keywords: *low birth weight, very low birth weight, extremely low birth weight, risk factors*